

**Diversification of output types in Business and Management:
challenging received wisdom¹**

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Overview

Outputs submitted to the UK Research Excellence Framework (REF) – which effectively determines a significant proportion of research funding for UK Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) - are dominated by a narrow range of output types. This is despite REF guidance which states that there are over 20 output types that are acceptable for submission (HEFCE, 2021). This limited diversity of output types is especially noticeable in the Business and Management (B&M) disciplines, represented by REF Unit of Assessment 17 (UoA17). This has led to calls for B&M researchers and those responsible for REF submissions to consider producing and submitting a wider range of output types than the peer-reviewed journal articles that dominate UoA submissions (Blackburn et al., 2024).

The UK '*Hidden REF*' initiative has championed the benefits of greater diversity of research outputs, with calls for more 'Non-Traditional Outputs' (NTOs) to be submitted to REF across all disciplines (Bisson, 2024; *The Hidden REF*, n.d.). The core argument is that research assessment which focuses on a narrow range of output types does not adequately represent the diversity of research conducted in universities, nor does it recognise the wide range of individuals and job roles that contribute to the production of research outputs and their wider impact.

Global initiatives that advocate broader reforms to research assessment systems, such as the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment ([CoARA](#)) and the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment ([DORA](#)) also promote greater diversity in the types of research output considered in the assessment process.

In particular, it has been argued that the predominant focus of B&M submissions on articles in typically a limited number of peer-reviewed journals has wider implications for the quality, impact and innovativeness of B&M research and for academic funding and career opportunities, especially for marginalised groups including researchers from the 'Global South' (Aguinis et al., 2022; Lindebaum & Hibbert, 2023; Sathish & Harzing, 2025; Wright, 2023). Potentially negative impacts on research culture have also been widely discussed, with suggestions that pressure on researchers to produce articles in 'leading' journals can lead to poor management practices and negative consequences for researchers' mental health (Bolden et al., 2025; Krieken, 2019; Ratle et al., 2020; Yeo et al., 2021).

On the other hand, an influential school of thought argues that the prevalent focus on journal articles and associated journal rankings, such as the [CABS Academic Journal Guide](#) (AJG) as means of assessing the research excellence is appropriate. For example, the established double-blind peer review process that underpins most 'reputable' journals represents, it is argued, the best possible (or least worst) way of assessing the rigour and robustness of research in B&M and similar disciplines (Hiebl, 2023; Morgan-Thomas et al., 2024; Rowlinson et al., 2015).

While peer review is widely accepted – including by REF, CoARA and DORA - as the most appropriate way of undertaking the challenging task of identifying and assessing the quality of research outputs, there is a considerable and growing debate about the use of journal metrics and rankings as proxy indicators of research quality (RoRI, 2022; Waltman et al., 2022; Watson, 2024). One argument revolves around the lack of any agreed basis on which to assess the quality of outputs that are not published in 'traditional' outlets, which include not only journals, but also books, book chapters and conference proceedings, with variations by discipline in

the representation of each. It is apparent that there are explicit or tacitly accepted hierarchies of output types, with articles in 'leading' journals at the top for many disciplines, and NTOs at the bottom, with exceptions for some disciplines. This appears to be the case for B&M, in relation not only to research assessment and REF, but also to processes such as the recruitment and promotion of academic staff (Anguyo, I., 2025; Ross-Hellauer et al., 2024; Rushforth & De Rijcke, 2024).

Much of the discussion is underpinned by notions of 'excellence' and debates around what constitutes 'excellent' research (Jong et al., 2022; Lindebaum & Hibbert, 2023; Moore et al., 2017; Pinar & Horne, 2022). For many, the peer review process is central to identifying excellent research and conversely to weeding out poor quality research which may be associated with inappropriate, unethical and/or fraudulent methods. A growing literature has begun to challenge the dominance of peer review as the main arbiter of academic excellence. Arguments revolve around the perceived shortcomings of the peer review process, for example the perpetuation of existing inequalities (Ma, 2022), the growth of so-called 'predatory' journals (Siler, 2018) and the challenges facing publishers and editors in attracting peer reviewers as the number of journals and article submissions continues to increase (Adam, 2025).

Several solutions which might address some of these shortcomings have been proposed and piloted. These include rewarding reviewers financially (and otherwise), greater recognition of peer review activities, widening the pool of peer reviewers, open and/or distributed peer review and standardising the review process to make it less onerous (Adam, 2025; Beres, 2024; Borger, 2018; Catterall, 2024). Diversifying the types of outputs considered as part of research assessment processes is one approach that has the potential to address these very real challenges, without losing or diminishing many of the claimed advantages of peer review.

This paper reviews evidence from recent UK REF exercises, and in particular submissions from B&M Units of Assessment, drawing on publicly available material and analysis of REF submission data. We explore the argument that REF submissions do not fully represent the diversity of output types, topics, methodologies and researcher characteristics that are evident in B&M departments and schools. We compare the pattern of REF submissions with the types of outputs recorded in the publicly available research repositories of selected B&M departments in UK HEIs. While there are shortcomings associated with the use of REF and institutional repository data, the evidence provides an emerging picture of the types of research outputs produced by UK B&M researchers, a large proportion of which do not appear in large-scale research evaluation exercises such as the REF.

We then consider the possible reasons for such an imbalance, and discuss the potential consequences for the diversity, innovativeness, quality and impact of B&M research and for the B&M research community. Finally, we introduce a possible way forward in the form of a pilot project within a small UK B&M department, drawing on expertise from disciplines that have significant experience of assessing the quality of 'non-traditional' outputs. In so doing, we make some suggestions as to how ingrained resistance to research assessment reform – including challenges to the acceptance of more diversified research outputs - might be addressed.

B&M outputs submitted to the UK Research Excellence Framework

REF 2001

(Geary et al., 2004) analyse data from the predecessor to REF, the Research Assessment Exercise (RAE) using data from the 2001 exercise. They observe that 80 per cent of just under 10,000 submissions to the B&M panel (then UoA19) were in the form of journal articles, with a particular focus on a limited number of journals such as those featured on the *Financial Times* list (Financial Times, 2016). In contrast, 508 submissions (5 per cent) were authored or edited books, 863 (9 per cent) were book chapters and 295 (3 per cent) were conference contributions. Only 303 outputs fell outside of these categories, including – perhaps surprisingly for the B&M discipline – only 80 reports to external bodies.

Analysis of the quality scores (on a seven-point scale of 0 to 5*) awarded by the RAE panel to each submitted output suggests little difference between the five main types of output, with a mean score of 5.03 for edited books, 4.84 for journal articles, 4.83 for authored books, 4.75 for book chapters and 4.66 for conference contributions. On the face of it, these results challenge the prevailing assumption that the average quality of journal articles is significantly higher than that of other types of output. Indeed ‘other forms of accessible output’ recorded the highest mean score of 5.82, albeit based on only 184 out of 10,000 submissions.

The authors go on to analyse the RAE scores awarded to articles submitted to the top 20 most frequently cited journals for B&M in the 2001 RAE. The overall mean score for the 1551 outputs in these journals was 5.4, higher than the 4.84 mean score for all outputs, lending some support to the argument that output quality (as measured by REF scores) varies by the perceived quality of individual journals. However, even within the ‘top 20’ journals, mean RAE scores range from 5.7 to 4.2, suggesting considerable variation among the journals that appear most popular with RAE-submitting institutions.

Further investigation provides ostensible support for the existence of a positive relationship between RAE scores and the ranking of journals by external organisations such as the *Financial Times* FT-40². However, it may be that there is a bi-directional relationship between journal rankings and RAE scores (ranking organisations are likely to take account of REF scores in judging journal quality and *vice versa*) and, as the authors acknowledge:

... the editorial policies of certain ... high rated journals may have exercised considerable influence on the direction of management research ... The interplay between editorial policies and the tactics of institutions making submissions to the RAE is likely to affect the types of knowledge that are valued in the Business and Management field (Geary, Marriott and Rowlinson, 2014: 109).

REF2014

Analysis of B&M submissions and scores for REF2014 undertaken by Pidd & Broadbent (2015) reveals similar patterns to those found for the 2001 RAE. The number of submitted outputs increased from around 10,000 to almost 12,000, of which 95 per cent were categorised as journal articles. This represents an increase in both the absolute and relative importance of journal articles over the 13-year

² The CABS Academic Journal Guide (AJG) did not exist at the time of the 2001 RAE.

period between these two national research assessment exercises that have been subject to this type of analysis.

Conversely, 'non-journal' publications made up a very small proportion of B&M output submissions in 2014. Books accounted for 165 outputs, book chapters 179, conference contributions 52 and 31 outputs were categorised as research reports for external bodies. Only one piece of statistical software was submitted (by Herriot-Watt University).

The authors point out that 'the sub-panel based its assessment of the quality of outputs on the criteria of originality, significance and rigour, and did not use journal lists for this purpose' (574). Nonetheless, the paper proceeds to examine the relationship between REF scores for individual outputs and the ranking of journals according to the most recent version of the ABS list (subsequently known as the CABS Academic Journal Guide, AJG). Based on a sample of 1000 outputs, the analysis found that 'about half the sample of outputs were awarded the same REF grade as their ABS journal rank. Slightly more than one-third scored below and one in seven scored above' (574). Clearly, there is some degree of broadly positive correlation between journal rankings and REF scores, but the relationship is not strong or predictable, leading Pidd and Broadbent (2015: 574) to warn that:

'The dangers of sole reliance on the ABS list or any other list for the full range of work covered by the sub-panel are very clear ... This may suggest that an inappropriate emphasis on journal papers leads to the non-submission of very highly quality research written up in books and monographs.'

REF2021

Analysis of 2021 REF submissions and results for UoA17 by Blackburn et al. (2024) found that of the approximately 13,000 unique outputs submitted (another notable increase over time), the overwhelming majority were journal articles. The highest GPA scores (calculated as the mean of the scores of 1 to 4 awarded to each output) were recorded for journal articles, and the lowest for conference contributions (Table 6, p. 442). This ostensibly supports the argument that the quality of peer-reviewed journal articles is typically higher than that of other output types. However, the small number of NTOs among the 13,000 submitted outputs provides only a limited basis on which to judge the relative quality of outputs beyond the overwhelming majority represented by journal articles, books, chapters and conference contributions. In line with previous analyses of this type, the authors note:

'We have ... reported that the overwhelming output types submitted were journal articles, and there is a concern that other types of output – such as books and/research monographs – are squeezed out of the set of admissible output types'. (Blackburn et al., 2024: 446)

Morgan-Thomas et al. (2024) undertook a detailed statistical analysis of REF2021 results for B&M with the primary objective of identifying differences between institutions that had or had not signed the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA, 2013). Using approaches based on algorithms and regression analysis to estimate the REF panel scores for individual outputs, they examine the relationship between journal rankings such as the CABS AJG and the REF scores, based on expert peer review. They conclude that:

... journal rank is positively associated with the expert scores in business and management and that (a) this relationship does not differ for institutions that declare adherence to DORA principles, and (b) it is stronger for prestige journals (Morgan-Thomas et al., 2024)

These findings - using methods different to those employed by Pidd & Broadbent (2015) and (Blackburn et al., 2024) - throw some doubt on the argument that journal rankings can be a poor proxy for the quality of individual outputs. The authors challenge proponents of responsible research assessment to consider how declarations such as DORA might be converted more effectively into research assessment practice, and to examine more closely how the unconscious use by expert peer reviewers of proxies such as journal rankings might be mitigated.

In relation to the Leeds Trinity University CoARA-funded pilot exercise, this includes (a) encouraging institutions to submit a greater proportion of NTOs to exercises such as REF; (b) incorporating NTOs more fully into internal processes such as recruitment and promotion and (c) enhancing the confidence, capacity and capability of peer reviewers to assess the quality of NTOs. We now turn to look at these issues in more depth.

What types of NTOs are submitted to REF?

The literature review demonstrates that, in line with prevailing approaches to research assessment in B&M, discussion and analysis of RAE/REF results have focused almost exclusively on journal publications, with the main questions revolving around the utility and desirability of using metrics such as journal impact factors, rankings or citation scores to assess the quality of individual articles. Some comparisons of quality assessment between articles, books, chapters and conference contributions have been undertaken, with inconclusive findings to date.

In contrast, little attention has been paid to B&M outputs that fall outside of these dominant categories. There are a few possible explanations for this:

- The focus of research assessment literature on articles (and to a lesser extent books and conference contributions) reflects a circular and self-perpetuating dominance of established output types, making it difficult for NTOs to 'break through' into the mainstream.
- The nature of the REF, and in particular the incentive for institutions to submit samples of outputs that they believe will maximise the probability of obtaining high quality ratings, mitigates against risk-taking in relation to the type of outputs submitted (Research Professional, 2025).
- Until 2021, only outputs authored by academics with 'significant responsibility for research' (SRR) were eligible for submission to REF. This is likely to exclude outputs produced by less research-active staff and those on professional service rather than academic contracts, potentially reducing the diversity of output types submitted³.

³ The proposed rules for submission to REF2029 which will 'decouple' individual from institutional contributions mean that, in principle, a wider range of authors and possibly outputs might be submitted (Research England, 2023).

- A corollary of the above is that a significant proportion of outputs that fall outside of the most common types submitted to REF, are produced by academics in B&M schools and departments but are not typically submitted to REF and are therefore largely invisible. A sizeable proportion of B&M outputs, much of which may be of high quality, is effectively hidden from view.

We examined in more depth the 85 outputs submitted to UoA17 for REF2021 that can be categorised as NTOs, i.e.

‘... those that, for a variety of reasons, are not communicated through “traditional” platforms such as journal articles, conference proceedings, monographs, and books’ [White Paper - The Hidden REF](#)

In brief, the vast majority of the 85 ‘NTOs’ took the form of Working Papers (58) or Research Reports for External Bodies (24), with only three outputs falling outside of the ‘traditional’ written word format – one piece of software, a translation and an unpublished conference presentation. This provides further support to the notion that the pattern of B&M outputs submitted to REF is narrow, even in relation to the range of written output types than we might expect to observe in a discipline such as B&M. Nonetheless, it seems surprising that no or very few B&M outputs were submitted in the categories of software, website content, digital or visual media or research data sets and databases, all of which are acceptable formats for REF.

Table 1: Number of B&M ‘non-traditional outputs’, REF 2014 and 2021

REF Code	Output type	2014	2021
G	Software	1	1
N	Research report for external body	31	24
R	Scholarly edition	-	1
T	Other	2	1
U	Working paper	103	58
V	Translation	-	1
	TOTAL (%) ‘NTOs’ SUBMITTED	137 (1.1%)	85 (0.5%)
	TOTAL OUTPUTS SUBMITTED	12,202	16,038

Source: [Results and submissions : REF 2021](#), [Results & submissions : REF 2014](#)

While recognising the small size of the sample of NTOs in B&M, it is notable that such submissions appear to have originated from a range of institution types, including several business schools that are generally recognised as ‘research intensive’, and might be expected to focus heavily on ‘high ranking’ journal articles (Appendix 1).

The titles of the NTO outputs submitted to UoA17 in REF2029 (Appendix) do not reveal any clear pattern in relation to broad subject area, research topic etc. Further analysis may reveal more, but it appears on first sight that B&M NTOs submitted to REF are not significantly different to 'typical' output types in any obvious way.

REF analysis: conclusions

This preliminary analysis suggests it is reasonable to surmise that many 'non-traditional' outputs (NTOs) – some of which may be regarded as 'high quality' - are not submitted to or reviewed by REF, possibly because institutions are reluctant to submit them. Indeed, the few B&M NTOs submitted to REF appear little different in nature to more 'traditional' peer-reviewed journal articles, books and chapters. It may be the case that the pattern of output types becomes self-fulfilling over time, as researchers tend to focus their 'best' work on journal articles (and articles in 'leading' journals in particular), with institutional and disciplinary policies, practices and cultures incentivising them to do so.

The trajectory of REF submissions reported in the literature reviewed here – in particular the increasing proportion of journal articles - appears to support such an interpretation. This accentuates the challenges associated with the desire among some groups to diversify research outputs, potentially disadvantages researchers who utilise NTOs to disseminate their work and arguably disincentivises creativity and innovation in research. Moreover, given the limited readership of journal articles among practitioners and policymakers, the relative homogeneity of types of output risks diluting the impact of research beyond the academic community.

Output recorded in institutional repositories: exploratory analysis

One positive side-effect of recent changes in rules for REF is that all submitted outputs must be available as Open Access, apart from in a very limited number of circumstances (Research England, 2024). While this rule applies only to outputs submitted to REF, institutions and individuals have become more efficient and effective in recording outputs in institutional repositories such as [PURE](#). This enables a more thorough – although not necessarily fully comprehensive and accurate – picture to be created of the range of research outputs produced across UK B&M schools or departments.

As an exploratory exercise, we collected data from several institutions that use the PURE system for recording and sharing their research outputs. This is primarily a convenience sample, but it serves to illustrate the potential for using data from such repositories to undertake more rigorous analysis of research and publishing patterns across HE.

One advantage of using PURE repositories for this exploratory analysis is that they use a common set of codes to categorise outputs by type. This helps with cross-institutional comparisons, but it relies on an implicit assumption that institutions and individuals are consistent in recording and categorising their outputs. Analysis at the disciplinary level also relies on institutions being broadly consistent in aligning organisational units with accepted disciplinary units such as the REF UoAs. This is a particular issue for B&M research, which does not always fall within business or management departments. Conversely, the multi-disciplinary nature of many

business schools means that many outputs produced by researchers fall outside of the B&M category for REF⁴.

Furthermore, not all PURE entries represent unique individual outputs, due to the recording of multiple authors from the same institution and due to the possibility that the same (or very similar) outputs might be presented in different formats (e.g. conference presentation, working paper, book chapter). Finally, the time periods over which output information is collected and reported in repositories are likely to vary between institutions.

Notwithstanding these limitations, exploration of PURE repositories provides some additional intelligence to inform the discussion about the reasons for, and the consequences of, the dominance of journal articles in relation to REF and related assessments of the quality of B&M research. Table 2 summarises the pattern of output types for eight selected business and/or management schools or departments.

There is considerable variation between the selected institutions in terms of the pattern of outputs recorded, with the percentage accounted for by articles varying between 70 and 44, in all cases well below the 80-95 per cent reported for REF UoA17/19. While this evidence is by no means conclusive, for the reasons noted above, there is some reason to believe that books, book chapters and conference papers form a greater proportion of the outputs produced by B&M researchers than is suggested by the pattern of REF submissions.

At the other end of the scale. NTOs account for up to one fifth of the B&M outputs recorded in institutional repositories, suggesting some potential benefits of investigating the nature and quality of such outputs compared with the typically more 'highly regarded' peer reviewed journal articles. This is a challenging undertaking, given that there exist no accepted criteria by which to estimate the quality of such outputs, in the way that REF panel scores have been used in some studies as proxies for expert assessment.

As part of the research for the LTU CoARA pilot project, we reviewed the 16 NTOs recorded in the Leeds Trinity PURE repository for B&M⁵. The breakdown is presented in Table 3.

Further investigation of the detailed entries reported in Table 3 reveals that several outputs fall into the discipline of Law and are therefore outside the scope of this study. In four cases, outputs had been misclassified and should have been allocated to more 'traditional' categories such as journal articles or conference contributions. We review briefly below some illustrative examples of 'Non-Traditional Outputs' produced by B&M researchers at Leeds Trinity University.

⁴ One of the authors was REF lead for a large business school for the 2021 exercise. Outputs submitted by colleagues from the school were spread across four different Units of Assessment, including Tourism, Nutrition and Built Environment.

⁵ Note that, since September 2025, the LTU School of Business was merged with the School of Law

Table 2: Types of B&M output recorded by repositories

Category	Leeds Trinity	% York	% Huddersfield	% Glasgow Caledonian	Kings College London	Edge Hill	% Queens Belfast	Lancaster	%							
Article	73	48.7	2304	54.5	666	66.9	1235	43.9	3256	70.3	388	49.6	2258	57.5	9028	53.2
Chapter	23	15.3	405	9.6	141	14.2	629	22.4	463	10.0	112	14.3	359	9.1	1891	11.1
Paper	23	15.3	604	14.3	1	0.1	115	4.1	19	0.4	88	11.3	213	5.4	847	5.0
Book	6	4	156	4	24	2	103	4	141	3	31	4	167	4	641	4
Article	6	4	17	0	3	0	99	4	25	1	7	1	52	1	114	1
Conference contribution	3	2.0	135	3.2	34	3.4	95	3.4	162	3.5	30	3.8	98	2.5	2774	16.3
Other (NTO)	16	10.7	603	14.3	126	12.7	535	19.0	567	12.2	126	16.1	779	19.8	1673	9.9
TOTAL	150	100	4224	100	995	100	2811	100	4633	100	782	100	3926	100	16968	100

Source: PURE repositories, websites of selected institutions

Table 3: Non-Traditional Outputs in Business, Management and Law: Leeds Trinity University

Poster	3
Encyclopaedia/dictionary	2
Abstract	2
Commissioned report	1
Book/film/article review	1
Editorial	1
Special issue	1
Patent	1
Doctoral thesis	1
Other	3

Source: PURE repository, Leeds Trinity University

1. Sand play for playful learners (workshop)

Based on sand play methods used with primary school children, this workshop demonstrates an intervention based on sand tray work for problem solving. This intervention is designed to bring the abstract ideas and issues to the forefront through sculpture and creative sand play. Participants bring their own questions to the workshop and use kinetic sand play with a variety of toys to mould and discover solutions by re-imagining their problems in a playful way. The subsequent 're-reading and re-telling' of the sculpture allows participants to make sense of their ideas, find new solutions and ways forward and communicate effectively.

[Sand play for problem solving - Leeds Trinity University Research Portal](#)

2. Mind.Set.Act. (patent)

In recent years Entrepreneurship Education (EE) has become prevalent throughout Higher Education (HE), with a proliferation of programming for learners from Undergraduate to Post-experience studies. Despite the rapid scaling of provision, the majority of extant EE offerings demonstrate little conceptual evolution and development from early programs. Many approaches fall short of enabling the cognitive and behavioral change so critical to supporting entrepreneurial action ... we consider the concept of entrepreneurial mindset (EM) as a framing for EE programming, conceptualizing it as an approach to support the development of multidimensional cognitive and emotional competences and behavioral outcomes to enable entrepreneurial value creating activity across a range of contexts.

[A competence development approach for entrepreneurial mindset in entrepreneurship education - University of Strathclyde](#)

3. The gig economy and the future of work (book/film/article review)

Over the last decade, the world of work has undergone significant changes with the phrase 'gig economy' becoming common parlance. However, what is meant by such an economy? ... as De Ruyter and Brown in their book point out, any discussion of 'gig work' is littered with value-laden terms; the UK Government favours the notion of 'flexible working', with many others viewing such arrangements as synonymous with 'precarious' contracts.

[The Gig Economy and The Future of Work - Pitchford - 2022 - New Technology, Work and Employment - Wiley Online Library](#)

4. Young people, employability and the induction process (report to external body)

This study is one of the Joseph Rowntree Foundation series on "Work and Opportunity" which addresses the changing face of work, its availability and accessibility for different sections of society. The report reviews the initial work experiences of young people entering the job market to discover how those early months of work affect their long-term employability, focusing on the experiences of both young people and employers of the process of induction.

The strengths of this report lie in its detailed case study work. It does not provide any easy answers but does succeed in surfacing and addressing the very real complexity of the induction process in the context of young people. Whilst the findings do not paint a uniform picture, a number of important issues emerge. For example, there appears to be very limited recognition of the specific needs of young recruits, particularly those entering their first job. Most employers adopt a "one size fits all" induction policy that may, in some cases, be to the detriment of young recruits.

[Young People, Employability and the Induction Process | Education + Training | Emerald Publishing](#)

Barriers to submission and assessment of NTOs

A rapid literature review and brainstorming discussion at the international [*'Responsible Research in Action'*](#) unconference in September 2025 identified a number of potential objections to the reform of research assessment that participants had encountered and/or have been noted in the literature. The exercise focused on research assessment reform more broadly, rather than specifically on the barriers to diversification of output types. Nonetheless, many of the potential objections listed below are relevant to the current discussion.

1. **Resistance to change** among stakeholders who feel that the current system works well, has led to the production of excellent research and has therefore been positive for the sector, benefitting institutions and those who work within them (*'if it isn't broke, don't fix it'*).
2. Research assessment reform is **expensive and resource-intensive** and is too time-consuming to implement. For example, many institutions do not have the **capacity or skills** to be able to review large numbers of research outputs using qualitative rather than quantitative approaches.
3. Lack of **effective measures** of the quality of 'non-standard' outputs.
4. **Risks of 'gaming' and 'overselling'** of the quality of some types of research outputs, for example through claims made in Narrative CVs.
5. Reform of research assessment may disadvantage those who have followed the 'old way' and therefore may lead to **unfairness in relation to rewards and career progression** (for both early career and established researchers).

In relation to the diversification of research outputs, particularly with reference to disciplines such as B&M for which formal research assessment has been tied closely to journal-related metrics, the main potential objections and barriers relate to the adoption of approaches and measures to review, assess and compare the quality of NTOs. A significant increase in the number of NTOs reviewed for research assessment exercises would generate the need for accepted measures of the quality of such outputs, the skills necessary to undertake such reviews fairly, the resources to review larger number of outputs and perhaps most significantly widespread acceptance of this type of assessment among those who are largely content with prevailing methods of research assessment.

For these reasons, it is important to engage with the understandable and often legitimate concerns raised by advocates of maintaining the status quo in relation to the assessment of the quality of B&M research outputs. One means of starting to address the objections set out above is to undertake pilot projects to demonstrate how the quality of NTOs might be assessed in ways that are acceptable to broad groups of stakeholders. Projects initiated by DORA and the *Hidden REF* are starting to develop evidence-based material, and further work is needed to build a convincing case in the context of B&M specifically. For this reason, Leeds Trinity University, with support from the CoARA Boost Cascade programme, undertook a pilot study to explore how B&M NTOs might be evaluated effectively - building on methods used by disciplines for which such outputs are relatively common - and to consider how such approaches can be incorporated into institutional research strategies.

Changing policy and practice through addressing common objections

A key aim of the LTU CoARA Boost pilot project was to develop approaches to influencing the direction of the institution's research policy towards recognition and incorporation of NTOs as important elements of the collective research effort. This also ties into the *Hidden REF* objective of increasing the number of NTOs submitted, and recognising the contribution of diverse colleagues in addition to those employed specifically as academic researchers.

Incorporating diverse research outputs into institutional research strategies presents challenges in the context of multiple pressures and priorities facing HEIs in the UK and elsewhere. There is an understandable temptation for institutions to conform to existing norms and to avoid the perceived risks associated with instigating significant changes to research assessment frameworks and processes. Advocates of increasing the focus on diverse and 'non-traditional' research outputs within institutional research strategies need to acknowledge the objections and concerns summarised in this paper, and to devise approaches that have the potential to address these concerns. Taking each area of concern in turn:

'The current system works perfectly well, so why change it?'

Our exploratory research has demonstrated that there is no clear and unequivocal relationship between types of output and the 'excellence' of the research reported in those outputs, using accepted processes of peer review (such as that used for the REF) as indicators of research quality. Some studies have identified a degree of positive correlation between assessed research quality and type of output, but this is by no means definitive and there are many examples of high-quality research presented in outlets beyond the peer-reviewed journals that dominate REF B&M submissions. Moreover, it can be argued that peer-reviewed journals are not always the most appropriate outlets for some types of research, but researchers and institutions tend to concentrate on journal outputs precisely because of their established dominance within the research assessment system. Such risk-averse behaviour may be understandable, but it is important for researchers and institutional leaders to recognise the potential of non-traditional outputs to demonstrate excellent research. The literature reviewed in this paper, and the pilot case studies developed at LTU, provide supporting evidence to challenge the 'if it isn't broke, don't fix it' narrative. We are not arguing, at least in the short term, for institutions to move away wholesale from the dominant model. However, acknowledging that the current system excludes some research that may be assessed as excellent, and taking some risks with submission of 'excellent' NTOs, would be a first step in the direction of more balanced consideration of diverse B&M outputs.

Limited capacity, skills and/or funding to implement research assessment reform

This is a non-trivial issue in relation to wider calls for reforms of the research assessment system. Diversification of the range of output types considered within the assessment system is likely to result in a significant increase in the number of outputs to be reviewed at disciplinary and institutional level. Our analysis of institutional repositories suggests that around 50 per cent of B&M outputs take the form of peer-reviewed journal articles. Given that consideration for REF submission

focuses almost exclusively on this type of output, assessors at UoA level may need to consider up to twice as many outputs to ensure the inclusion of the full range of diverse output types. This will also be the case for related activities such as performance review and assessment of promotion applications. Inevitably, this will require additional resources in terms of the time and expertise of assessors and research-adjacent colleagues to establish, manage and implement revised assessment and reporting processes. External support may also be needed.

Some investment will be required in training for assessment of diverse outputs. This should not need to start from scratch, however; knowledge and skills can be developed through building on interdisciplinary links and through cross-institutional collaboration. Initiatives such as *Hidden Ref* and the [Diversifying Output Types](#) project at the University of Liverpool are excellent sources of information and expertise. Broadening the range of output types to be assessed also provides an opportunity to engage wider and more diverse groups of internal and external reviewers in addition to those with experience of reviewing journal articles.

Lack of effective measures of the quality of 'non-standard' outputs

Researchers and research leaders within the B&M disciplines are very familiar with the use of journal-based indicators, citations, journal rankings (such as the CABS AJG) and other quantitative measures derived from bibliometric analysis (such as the h-index) to provide direct or proxy indicators of the quality of outputs, individual researchers, research teams or indeed institutions such as business schools. This accounts for, and indeed can be argued to perpetuate, the dominance of journal outputs in assessment exercises such as the REF, despite growing evidence that non-journal outputs and NTOs (a) account for around half of all B&M research outputs and (b) in many cases represent high-quality research as determined by accepted peer review processes.

Furthermore, many other disciplines rely much less heavily than B&M on peer-reviewed journal articles to provide assessments of research quality. Humanities disciplines such as History and Literature tend to focus primarily on long-form outputs such as books, while some science disciplines place considerable emphasis on peer-reviewed outputs produced for 'prestigious' conferences. In disciplines such as creative arts, film, drama, music, journalism and media studies, a wide range of outputs that are 'non-traditional' for B&M and other disciplines, are routinely assessed for their quality, including for national exercises such as REF. It is therefore not strictly correct to argue that agreed methods of assessing NTOs do not exist; they are simply much less known or utilised in B&M and related disciplines. A key component of the LTU CoARA Boost pilot project is to learn from colleagues in creative arts, film and related disciplines how the approaches they adopt to research assessment might be adopted or adapted to enable B&M NTOs to be evaluated in a robust, consistent and fair way. The project is also drawing on the considerable and growing body of work undertaken and supported by the *Hidden REF*. In so doing, we plan to start to address the argument that we do not have effective measures to assess non-standard or non-traditional outputs, and to share potential approaches that can be applied to B&M and similar disciplines.

Risks of gaming and overselling

This is an issue for all forms of research assessment but is especially prevalent for assessment based largely on journal metrics. For example, commentators have identified an active market in relation to citations and the growth of predatory journals (Linacre, 2025) and increasing charges for open access all give rise to the potential for gaming. Lists of prestigious journals such as the FT-50 also generate the possibility of overselling the quality of specific outputs that happen to be published in these outlets, within limited use of peer review in the assessment process.

The diverse nature of the assessment process for NTOs, and the limited role of quantitative metrics in such processes, arguably reduces the potential for gaming and overselling. However, it is important for researchers and research leaders to be alert to this potential and to ensure that assessment of NTOs is seen as open, consistent and fair.

Danger of unfairness and limited researcher diversity

There is considerable evidence that research assessment based primarily on journal-based metrics confers an advantage on certain types of researchers (white, male, based in the Global North) over others, including women, researchers from minority ethnic groups, disabled researchers and those based in the Global South. There is also an argument to suggest that conventional approaches to research assessment can favour 'proven' research methods (often quantitative) and disincentivise qualitative and more innovative methodologies (Ma, 2022).

It is by no means clear from existing evidence that encompassing more diverse output types will result in fairer representation of the researcher base and more innovative research methods, but there is some reason to believe that this is likely to be the case. Further research into and experimentation with evaluation of NTOs should provide further evidence and it will be important for stakeholders to ensure that equality, diversity and inclusion are given appropriate priority in reformed processes of evaluating research outputs.

Conclusion

This paper has reviewed literature and presented evidence to suggest that there is considerable potential to diversify the types of output that are considered in the assessment of research quality in Business & Management (B&M) and related disciplines. There is emerging evidence that the peer-reviewed journal articles that dominate submissions to the UK Research Excellence Framework are not necessarily fully representative of the diversity and quality of outputs produced by academics in B&M schools and departments. We have argued that the inclusion of a wider range of Non-Traditional Outputs (NTOs) in research assessment exercises would result in a more accurate picture of B&M research and would contribute to wider efforts to reform research assessment systems. We acknowledge that there are some barriers to the adoption of such an approach, and we have set out some potential directions of travel that will help to shift research assessment policies and practices in what we believe to be a desirable direction.

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Appendix 1: Institutions submitting at least one NTO to REF2021 UoA17

- Aston University
- Bath Spa University
- City, University of London
- Edinburgh Napier University
- Heriot-Watt University
- Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine
- Leeds Beckett University
- London Business School
- Manchester Metropolitan University
- Middlesex University
- Oxford Brookes University
- Robert Gordon University
- The London School of Economics and Political Science
- The Open University
- The University of Birmingham
- The University of Chichester
- The University of Cumbria
- The University of Lancaster
- The University of Leicester
- The University of Liverpool
- The University of Manchester
- The University of Reading
- The University of Warwick
- University College London
- University of Aberdeen
- University of Dundee
- University of Durham
- University of Edinburgh
- University of Glasgow
- University of Hertfordshire
- University of Lincoln
- University of Newcastle upon Tyne
- University of Oxford
- University of Southampton
- University of Strathclyde
- University of Sussex
- University of the West of Scotland

Appendix 2: Titles of ‘Non-Traditional Outputs’ submitted to REF2021, UoA17

Pre-Pack Empirical Research : Report to the Graham Review by the University of Wolverhampton	
Regulation of Internet Pornography : Issues and Challenges	
An evaluation of three One Team initiatives: Halcon, North Taunton and Wellington	
Insurance Between Firms: The Role of Internal Labor Markets	
Unkettling the unions? An action research study of surmounting the Trade Union Act 2016 in the UK higher education sector	
PDSLASSO & LASSOPACK : Stata module for post-selection and post-regularization OLS or IV estimation and inference	
BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2019	
Unpacking the performance effects of coupling in the environment-organization and intraorganizational levels	
Improving progression in low-paid, low-skilled retail, catering and care jobs	
CEO Turnover in LBOs: The Role of Boards	
Forest Through the Trees: Building Cross-Sections of Stock Returns	
Heterogeneity in HMMs: Allowing for Heterogeneity in the Number of States	
Operating Leverage over the Business Cycle	
Recovering Global Supply Chains from Sourcing Interruptions: The Role of Sourcing Strategy	
The Authenticity Challenge: How a Values-Affirmation Exercise Can Engender Authentic Leadership	
Mend the Gap: The Independent Review into Gender Pay Gaps in Medicine in England	
Reform of Rules on EU VAT Rates	
A comparative analysis of IDB approaches supporting SMEs: assessing results in the Brazilian manufacturing sector	
R&D smoothing: evidence and some theory	
Gender and Higher Education Leadership: Researching the careers of top management programme alumni	
The capability and competency requirements of auditors in today’s complex global business environment	
Delivering performance : the capital market framing of financial numbers from a preparer perspective	
Long-term contracting with time-inconsistent agents	
Price and volume dynamics in bubbles	
Police Knowledge Fund Review	
Leveling up? An inter-neighborhood experiment on parochialism and the efficiency of multi-level public goods provision	
Manhood Peninsula Destination Management Plan 2018-2023	
Brexit: Implications for the rural North of England	
Review of Issues Related to Methods, Criteria and Indicators for Widening Actions	
Researching Entrepreneurial Leadership: A Review and Research Agenda	
Uncertainty shocks in emerging economies : a global to local approach for identification	
The Worker : Dominion and Form	
A New Industry on a Skewed Playing Field: Supply Chain Relations and Working Conditions in UK Garment Manufacturing	
The effects of menopause transition on women’s economic participation in the UK	
A Wiener–Kolmogorov Filter for Seasonal Adjustment and the Cholesky Decomposition of a Toeplitz Matrix	

Impact of Family Planning Policy on Gender Inequality: Evidence from China	
Markets and Markups: A New Empirical Framework and Evidence on Exporters from China	
Too Big to Care, Too Small to Matter: Macrofinancial Policy and Bank Liquidity Creation	
Communications in Proxy Contests	
Value for money in a sick PFI hospital: a Gramscian perspective	
Atomic dynamic flow games : adaptive versus nonadaptive agents	
Central Bank Communication and the Yield Curve	
Disentangling the share buyback puzzle : post-event insider trades	
Effects of immigration on investment	
On aggregate fluctuations, systemic risk, and covariance of firm-level activity	
R&D investment under financial constraints and competition	
The neglected piece of health IT assimilation : unveiling the learning trajectories of rotating physicians	
The shadow disintermediation of risk-sensitive capital	
This cloud has a silver lining : economic crisis and technological exploration	
Unconventional monetary policy and covered interest rate parity deviations : is there a link?	
Understanding consumer browsing patterns : a sequence analysis approach	
How Catastrophic Innovation Failure Affects Organizational and Industry Legitimacy: The 2014 Virgin Galactic Test Flight Crash	
Spillover Effects and Freemium Strategy in Mobile App Market	
That's Not Fair: Tariff Structures for Electric Utilities with Rooftop Solar	
A Coding Typology to study dyadic interactions in International Negotiations : Extending the IPA model	
CEO Political Ideology, Shareholder Primacy and Dividend Policy	
Do the Managers of Global Real Estate Mutual Funds Have Skills?	
Tax Incentives for CO2-EOR in the UK Continental Shelf	
The Intergenerational Mobility of White Working Class Boys : A Quantitative Analysis	
Income stratification and the measurement of interdistributional inequality between multiple groups	
International trade, non-trading firms and their impact on labour productivity.	
Social justice and career development	
Sustainable Debt Restructuring in the time of Covid 19: Investment and Non-Elite Participation	
Gender and unemployment. Analysis of Understanding Society: the UK Household Longitudinal Survey	
The Global Syndemic of Obesity, Undernutrition, and Climate Change : The Lancet Commission report	
Third sector capacity building cluster: taking part? [Economic and Social Research Council Impact Report]	
U.S. monetary policy normalization and global interest rates	
Quality Differentiation and Spatial Clustering among Restaurants	
Orchestrating Major Projects: The Tasks of Leadership for Government Ministers	
The Museum Leaders' Report	
An empirical model of screening rule choice	
Automation and the displacement of labor by capital: Asset pricing theory and empirical evidence	
Can AI help in crowdsourcing? testing alternate algorithms for idea screening in crowdsourcing contests	

Death by Committee? An Analysis of Corporate Board (Sub-) Committees	
How the flexible firm expands with online labor platforms: Theorizing online labor platforms as a new model for sourcing high-skilled knowledge work	
How to Improve Tax Compliance? Evidence from Population-Wide Experiments in Belgium	
On the Quantity and Quality of Girls Fertility, Parental Investments, and Mortality	
The structure and relations of banking systems: the UK experience and the challenges of 'levelling-up'	
Unions' surging sword of justice repulsed? Pay inequality and the advance and retreat of British unionism 1960-2000	
Examining the Effectiveness of Support for UK Wave Energy Innovation since 2000 : Lost at Sea or a New Wave of Innovation?	
Riskwork in the construction of Heathrow Terminal 2	
Seeking transparency whilst embracing ambiguity: skip level leadership dynamics during strategic change	
'Decent Work' : The Employers' View	
Scotland's Local Authorities : Still 'Bastions of Decent Work'?	
Talent Management in Public Services in Scotland	